

with mesothelial cells. The epithelium of cervix uteri was strongly positive for PAS, Alcian Blue (pH 2.5) and PAS-Alcian Blue (pH 2.5) and moderate for lipids. This study showed the histomorphometrical changes in the cervix of ewe occur in the follicular and luteal phases which might be related to the fluctuation of estrogen and progesterone hormone.

References

Bancroft, J.D., Stevens, A. (1977) *Theory and practice of*

Histological Techniques. Churchill Livingstone, Edinburgh, London and New York.

Eurell, J.A. and Frappier B.L. (2006) *Dellman's Text book of Veterinary Histology*. 6th Edn. Wiley-Blackwell.

Luna, L.G. (1968) *Manual of Histological Staining Methods of the Armed Forces Institute of Pathology*. 3rd Edn. McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York.

Pearse, A.G.E. (1968) *Histochemistry: Theoretical and applied*. 3rd ed. Vol. I.

Snedecor, G.W. and Cochran, W.G. (1994) *Statistical methods*. 8th Edn. Oxford and IBH Publishing Co., New Delhi

Uppal, V. and Roy, K.S. (2002) *Indian J. Anim. Sci.*, **72**: 730.

Indian Vet. J., October 2012, 89 (10) : 72 - 74

Anatomy of the Pancreas of Domestic Cat (*Felis catus*)

P. Jagapathi Ramayya¹, A. Prasanth Babu, H.S. Patki and T.S. Chandrasekhara Rao

Department of Veterinary Anatomy and Histology, College of Veterinary Science, Sri Venkateswara Veterinary University, Tirupati 517 502, Andhra Pradesh

(Received : 22-10-2011;

Accepted : 12-12-2011)

The anatomical information of the pancreas of cat is found to be meager. Hence, the present study was undertaken to investigate the microanatomy of the pancreas of cat.

Materials and Methods

Microanatomical studies were conducted on the pancreas of six adult Indian domestic cats, which were brought to the Department of Pathology for postmortem examination. Pancreas was collected immediately after death and preserved in 10% neutral buffered formalin.

The tissue pieces were processed for paraffin sections of 5-6 micron thickness and the sections were subjected to Haematoxylin and Eosin staining method and Halami's modified aldehyde fuchsin staining method for different cells of endocrine pancreas (Bancroft and Gamble, 2008).

Results and Discussion

In cat pancreas was covered by a thin connective tissue capsule comprising of collagen fibres and adipose tissue. In the

¹Corresponding author : Email : drjagapathi_palla@yahoo.com

present study, the trabeculae arose from the capsule and divided the parenchyma into lobes and several lobules. These interlobar and interlobular septae were composed of fine collagen, reticular fibres, blood vessels and ducts.

The parenchyma consisted of exocrine and endocrine parts. The exocrine region formed bulk of the parenchyma, which was made up of pancreatic acini. These acini were packed together in an irregular manner with a few reticular fibres between them.

The pancreatic acinii were of varying shapes i.e., round, oval and irregular. They were composed of single layer of pyramidal secretory cells. These cells had two distinct zones. The inner zone (towards apex of the cell) was coarsely granular and contained red stained granules while the outer zone (towards base of the cell) appeared homogenous. The nuclei of acinar cells were spherical and located at different levels i.e more basal, basal and central positions in resting, active and exhausted phases respectively. These cells contained zymogen granules and they were eosinophilic in nature. Due to large number of granules nucleus was pushed towards the base.

Fig 1. Photomicrograph of endocrine portion of pancreas showing alpha cells (A), beta cells (B) and delta cells (D). Halami's aldehyde fuchsin x 40.

In the present study, pacinian corpuscles were observed in the pancreas of cat close the ducts and blood vessels. Kelly *et al.* (1985) reported that the pacinian corpuscles were occasionally found in the human pancreas. Kumamoto *et al.* (1988) suggested that pacinian corpuscles in cat pancreas acted as internal receptors detecting modifications in the duct wall by changes in pancreatic secretions and blood flow. Further, large oval parasympathetic ganglia were located in the interlobular connective tissue (King *et al.* 1989).

The endocrine part consisted of encapsulated areas, the islets of Langerhans having aggregations of pale staining cells. These islets were of two types viz., small and large. The smaller islets outnumbered the larger ones and these islets were irregular in shape. Islam (2010) reported round to oval islets in other domestic mammals. Sinusoidal capillaries were observed between the meshes of cellular cords.

The principal cells of islets of Langerhans were alpha (α), beta (β) and delta (δ) cells. They were differentiated with modified aldehyde fuchsin stain. Alpha (α) cells stained yellow and were observed at the periphery of islets of Langerhans. Beta (β) cells were predominantly seen at the centre of islets of Langerhans and were stained purple to violet in colour. Delta (δ) cells were rare in occurrence. They stained green and were scattered throughout the islets.

Summary

Microanatomical studies were conducted on the pancreas of six adult Indian domestic cats. The pancreas was covered by a thin connective tissue capsule comprising of collagen fibres. The trabeculae arose from the capsule dividing the parenchyma into lobes and several lobules. The parenchyma was divided into exocrine and endocrine regions. The exocrine region formed bulk of the parenchyma, which was made up of

pancreatic acini. They were lined by single layer of pyramidal secretory cells. Pacinian corpuscles and parasympathetic ganglia were observed in the pancreas of cat in interlobular connective tissue. The endocrine part islets of Langerhans showed alpha (α), beta (β) and delta (δ) cells. In these beta (β) cells were the most predominant and were located centrally. Alpha (α) cells were observed at the periphery and delta (δ) cells were rare in occurrence. They stained green and were scattered throughout the islets.

References

- Bancroft, J.D. and Gamble, M. (2008) *Theory and Practice of Histological Techniques*. 6th edn. Churchill Livingstone, Elsevier, Philadelphia. pp. 298.
- Islam S. (2010). *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology: The islets of Langerhans*. Springer, Heidelberg. pp. 31.
- Kelly, D.E., Wood, R.L. and Enders, A.C. (1985) *Bailey's textbook of Microscopic Anatomy*. 18th edn. Williams and Wilkins, Baltimore, pp. 582.
- King, B.F., Love, J.A. and Szurszewski, J.H. (1989) *J. Physiol.* **419**:379.
- Kumamoto, K., Ohkawa, Y., Ebara, S., Matsuura, T. and Takeda, H. (1988) *Bulletin Meiji Col. Orient. Med.* **4**: 43.

Indian Vet. J., October 2012, 89 (10) : 74 - 76

Heterologus Blood Transfusion in Anaemic Calves

Manoj Kumar Dwivedi, S.R.P. Sinha¹, Pallav Shekher, Bipin Kumar, Sucheta Sinha, Archana Kumari and K.G. Mandal

Department of Veterinary Medicine, Bihar Veterinary College, Patna 800014

(Received : 11-10-2010;

Accepted : 21-05-2011)

Effect of anaemia can be fatal in the absence of proper management. In practice, critically ill animals require emergent therapeutic measures before investigation of actual cause of disease. In cases where haemoglobin level falls below 6.00 g/dl life is threatened. Blood transfusion immediately revitalizes the affected animal as it provides adequate tissue oxygenation. In present experiment effect on 3 and 4 heterologus blood transfusion (HTB) was investigated on various haematological parameters in anaemic calves.

Materials and Methods

15 clinically anaemic cross-bred calves of different age or sex were selected on the basis of clinical symptoms and Hb level ($\leq 6\%$) from different farms and surrounding areas of Bihar Veterinary College, Patna and randomly divided into 3 groups, T₁, T₂ and T₃. Blood transfusion in experimental animals was carried as per plan, that, group T₁ received four blood transfusions from four different donors at 48 h intervals and group T₂ received three

¹Corresponding author : Email : sinhasrp@yahoo.com